

The Effect of Concentrate Containing Probiotics on Fermentation Characteristics and in vitro Nutrient Digestibility

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Abstract : The aim of the experiment was to evaluate the effect of probiotic addition in concentrate on fermentation characteristics and in vitro nutrient digestibility of the grass *Pennisetum purpureophoides*. Two strains lactic acid bacteria (LAB) i.e *Lactobacillus plantarum* and *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, and one strain yeast of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were used as probiotic. The probiotics was added at 2% and 4% (v/w) in the concentrate. The result showed the concentrate containing between 1.5×10^6 and 3×10^7 CFU/g of lactic acid bacteria and 3×10^3 CFU/g of *S. cerevisiae*. The DM, OM and NDF digestibility were higher ($P < 0.01$) in grass substrate with concentrate than in grass alone. Addition of probiotic in concentrate increased ($P < 0.01$) DM, OM and NDF compared to concentrate without probiotic. Total VFA and propionic acid concentrations were higher ($P < 0.01$) in grass substrate with concentrate than in grass alone. Concentration of acetic acid decreased ($P < 0.01$) in grass substrate with concentrate than in grass substrate alone. Addition of *L. plantarum* and *L. acidophilus* and *S. cerevisiae* in concentrate increased ($P < 0.01$) propionic acid concentration. It was concluded that addition of probiotic in concentrate increased propionic concentration and in vitro nutrient digestibility.

Keywords : by-products, concentrate, digestibility, probiotics

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